

Farmer Clusters: Landscape scale collaboration to address the biodiversity crisis on English farmland

Policy recommendations

To promote Farmer Clusters as an effective approach to improve biodiversity, environmental outcomes, and sustainability across farm landscapes the following policies are recommended:

- **Introduce group-based incentives within Agri-Environment Schemes (AES).** Develop and embed flexible incentives that reward collaborative action and enable collective results within AES. Build on successful pilots across Europe (e.g. in Switzerland and tested in the CONSOLE project) to embed group result-based payments and voluntary clustering as core elements of national policy, reinforcing both rural resilience and ecological benefits.
- **Enhance access to advice, training and monitoring tools.** Policy should prioritise funding for knowledge exchange platforms, tailored training and shared monitoring protocols, ensuring farmers have the information, tools and support needed to implement, assess and adapt their conservation efforts within their Farmer Clusters. Importantly access and knowledge of monitoring and training tools should also be shared with advisory networks to improve the materials reach to farmers. Consistency of approach across Farmer Clusters will build greater understanding of biodiversity and habitat management across regions and England.
- **Continued investment in, and development of, the Countryside Stewardship Facilitation Fund.** Government and rural development policies should continue to embed training, resourcing, and financing for Farmer Cluster facilitators as core elements of England’s agri-environmental programmes. However, we recommend the following reforms to England’s facilitation fund:
 - Refocusing the facilitation funding on outcomes achieved by Farmer Clusters (e.g. how many farmers participate in training events, how much land has signed up to the Farmer Cluster and what proportion of this has been handed over to nature) rather than the current auditing approach which requires facilitators to timesheet their groups activities.
 - Increase the duration of facilitation fund contracts from three years to a minimum of five years to support longer term impacts. Allowing facilitation funding to fund a mixture of one-to-one advice and group advice.
 - Include financial support for landscape biodiversity monitoring and evidence gathering.
 - Allowing Farmer Clusters more flexibility to adapt group activities to better meet the interests and needs of the group

Transformative impact of Farmer Clusters on farmland biodiversity

Farmland biodiversity is in decline, threatening both agroecosystem services and long-term food system resilience. While AES aim to reverse this trend, uptake and impact vary widely. Traditional top-down AES often fail to connect with farmers’ local realities, values, and identity. In contrast, the Farmer Cluster approach offers a promising alternative. Farmer Clusters empower farmers to achieve their farming and environmental goals. By working together under the guidance of a skilled facilitator, farmers can tackle landscape-level restoration and have a greater impact than any one individual could accomplish alone. Using a “bottom-up” approach, farmers identify their conservation priorities and choose which practices to implement collectively. This is an impactful way to address global issues

such as biodiversity conservation at the landscape scale. As well as the conservation benefits, Farmer Clusters can create support networks in rural communities, bridging gaps between policy-makers and farmers, and fostering both regional and national cohesion.

Figure 1 Corn Buntings have experienced steep declines in the UK and are one of the farmland bird species targeted by the Cranborne Chase Farmer Clusters (England) conservation efforts. Photo © Charlotte Foote

Approach and results

The **EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork** explores the potential to replicate the Farmer Cluster model across Europe to enhance farmland biodiversity at a continental scale. Between 2020 and 2021, eleven clusters, regrouping 124 farms, were established in eight countries: the UK, Austria, the Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Italy, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Spain, and varied in size, farming system, organisational structure, and the degree of connectivity between farms. Biodiversity-friendly practices introduced by the Farmer Clusters include the introduction of wildflower margins, meadow restoration, hedgerow and tree planting, and the installation of bat and bird boxes. Leaning on experiences from the FRAMEwork project, this policy brief explains how Farmer Clusters can play a role in promoting biodiversity, ecosystem services and sustainable farming practices; collaboration and knowledge exchange; and landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring.

Evidence of impact

By fostering collaboration among farmers within shared landscapes, Farmer Clusters serve as platforms for implementing sustainable practices, spurring innovation and enhancing ecological resilience.

- **Identity change drives lasting behaviour**

Facilitated Farmer Clusters allow farmers to reimagine their role in biodiversity conservation. Through trust and peer exchange, they transition from isolated efforts to collaborative, nature-friendly practices. This shift in identity—from compliance to stewardship—encourages long-term behavioural change. Interviews show that many farmers embraced terms like “nature-friendly farming” and developed a deeper sense of responsibility, turning sceptics into advocates and embedding conservation values in rural communities (Bohnet et al., 2025).

- **Tangible ecosystem benefits and sustainable practices**

Farmer Clusters can deliver real environmental gains—from improved soil health to increased biodiversity. Localised practices, such as zero tillage and cover cropping in *Scotland’s Buchan cluster*, enhance soil life and retention. In Austria flower strips and species-rich grasslands restore pollinator habitats and floral diversity. In France and Italy, clusters focused on improving natural pest control and sustainable farming, illustrating how collective action benefits both nature and agriculture. In England the *Cranborne Chase Farmer Cluster* focused on enhancing farmland bird populations through improving the quality, abundance and connectivity of AES habitats and hedgerows across the landscape, this has resulted in significant increases in farmland bird abundance (graph below) and richness compared to the baseline survey year (2021).

Figure 2 Predicted farmland bird species abundance per 100m

- **Landscape-scale biodiversity monitoring and citizen science**

Monitoring is vital for understanding the effectiveness of conservation measures and guiding result-based payments. FRAMEwork adapted tried and tested protocols used in existing monitoring schemes for use within Farmer Clusters, allowing farmers to assess changes in habitats and species across farms and between holdings. In addition, involving communities in data collection through citizen science methods creates a shared understanding of ecological changes across the landscape, build trust between farmers and the public, and foster a sense of shared purpose. They help farmers and communities alike to take ownership of the evidence base that guides biodiversity conservation, making it more relevant, resilient, and deeply rooted within rural areas.

Policy implications

Successful Farmer Clusters depend on a number of interlinked factors related to facilitation, trust, the way in which advice is provided, evidence of impact, knowledge, guidance and financial support. Evidence from the FRAMEwork project across Europe highlights how these elements can work together

to drive long-term conservation outcomes.

- **Refocusing Facilitation Funding on Measurable Outcomes**

To enhance the long-term effectiveness and impact of Farmer Clusters, facilitation funding should be reoriented away from an administrative, audit-heavy model—such as the current requirement for facilitators to track group activities via timesheets—and instead **prioritise tangible outcomes achieved by Farmer Clusters**. This could include metrics such as the number of farmers actively participating in training and advisory sessions, the total area of land incorporated into Farmer Cluster activities and the proportion of that land actively managed for nature recovery. Refocusing funding in this way would empower facilitators to use their time more effectively, tailor their support to the needs of individual farmers as well as the broader Farmer Cluster, and deliver more robust outcomes for biodiversity, climate resilience and rural communities.

- **Skilled facilitation is essential**

Facilitators are the linchpins of effective Farmer Clusters. They coordinate meetings, deliver training, monitor progress, and connect farmers with NGOs, researchers, and policymakers. Where facilitation was strong, trust and peer learning flourished; where it was weak, engagement declined. Well-resourced facilitators are vital for building cohesion, sustaining motivation, and ensuring lasting impact (Bohnet et al., 2025). Policy must prioritise **investment in facilitator training and support** to maintain momentum and avoid fragmentation.

- **Increase Facilitation Fund contract durations**

Currently facilitation funding contracts for Farmer Clusters are three years in duration, longer term contracts would support skilled facilitators to build stronger relationships and trust with farmers, enable long-term environmental planning and thus the delivery of long-term benefits for biodiversity and rural communities. Many of the Farmer Clusters established through the FRAMEwork project felt that the **establishment of trust was a significant driver of success**, which often took a **minimum of four years to establish**.

- **Provision of one-to-one and group advice**

Allowing facilitation funding to fund a mixture of one-to-one advice (e.g. for technical planning and grant applications) and group advice (e.g. to address broad topics such as landscape habitat connectivity) would maximise impact by improving farmer trust and engagement, learning and environmental outcomes.

- **Financial support for biodiversity monitoring**

Including support for landscape scale monitoring and evidence gathering is also recommended. This **would allow group members to see the effects of their efforts on the ground**, a key way to motivate engagement, and increases confidence that Farmer Clusters will be supported in the future. Support should prioritise consistent, cost-effective approaches (e.g. simple habitat quality indicators, identification and monitoring of relevant indicator species as proxies for biodiversity).

- **Access to knowledge, advice, and practical tools**

Farmers need more than goodwill—they need the right information at the right time and to feel that they are part of something bigger. Platforms like Recodo.io provide open-access training, biodiversity monitoring protocols, and stakeholder engagement resources that empower both facilitators and farmers. These tools enable the adoption of biodiversity-friendly practices and align local actions with broader conservation goals. Policy should ensure that such platforms are widely accessible, regularly updated and tailored to local contexts.

- **Incentives that support voluntary, collective action**

FRAMEwork findings show that schemes with voluntary collaboration consistently outperform mandatory Farmer Cluster participation. Clusters saw **higher engagement** when incentives allowed **flexible participation** and supported peer-led initiatives. Collective result-based payments enhanced conservation outcomes and **built peer accountability**. Particularly in high-risk settings, collective payments improved cooperation by leveraging the potential for collective risk-sharing. Policymakers should design incentive structures that are adaptable, locally relevant, and rooted in shared goals.

References / Further Reading

Bohnet, I., Thomas, F., Zagata, L., Hardy, C., Fritschle, M., Engel, S., & Kuhfuss, L. (2025). D6.1 Report on the impact of Cluster approach on Farmer's self-identity and behaviour (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15090426>).

To learn more about the FRAMEwork projects eleven Farmer Cluster, see <https://re-codo.io/page/farmer-clusters/farmer-cluster-finder>.

About this Policy Brief

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